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Role of Information Technology (IT) Sector in Indian Economy

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Abstract

Information Technology (IT) sector is considered to be the fastest growing sector of Indian economy, it has molded itself as the strengthening structure through adoption of emerging technologies including information of things, cybersecurity, machine learning and artificial intelligence. It holds a crucial position in the growth of the economy, and currently has a share of 7.4 percent in India's GDP and holds growth of 8.1 percent in export revenue and that is why nowadays it is considered as a corner stone of modern India. This paper has focused upon exploring the key growth drivers of IT sector, and to examine the revenue of IT/BPM sector in the GDP of the country. Further, it has also discussed the export of IT sector to that of overall export of the economy. India's IT-BPM sector (excluding e-commerce) is anticipated to grow by 15.5% to reach USD 227 billion in financial year 2021–2022, with exports accounting for USD 178 billion (E). The paper concludes that the revenue of information technology sector is expected to increase up to dollar 350 billion till 2026 and with the growth rate of 17.02 percent, export of information technology is set to reach a target of dollar 178 billion excluding hardware.

Keywords: IT/BPM sector, IT export, GDP, and Indian Economy.

Introduction

In the era of globalization and technology, Information technology sector has boosted the Indian economy to grow further and has immense significance in our economy. It has made a remarkable contribution to establishing the nation as a favored investment location for international investors and generating large numbers of job opportunities in India as well as. Emerging technologies are now providing top IT firms in India with a whole new range of opportunities after they demonstrated their ability to provide both on-shore and off-shore services to clients worldwide. The nation's affordable pricing for IT services, which is roughly three to four times less expensive than the US, continues to be its USP in the global sourcing market. The Indian IT/Software sector offers competitive pricing, excellent quality, high reliability, quick turnaround times, and, most importantly, the utilization of cutting-edge technology across the globe.

The Indian IT/ITeS sector holds a dominant position globally and has been gradually boosting exports and opening up job possibilities. Large employment prospects have also been created by the IT/software sector, which is predicted to employ 5.1 million professionals by FY 2021–2022, an increase of 4,45,000 workers (E). 36% (1.8 million) of the entire industry workforce is made up of women.

Under automatic route up to hundred percent (100%) foreign direct investment is allowed in software development and computer consultancy services, market research services, business and management consultancy services, data processing, software supply services, technical testing and analysis services. The computer software and hardware sector draw the second-highest amount of foreign direct investment. Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) investment has risen by 62.5% since 2021 and is predicted to reach \$6.5 billion in 2022. There are more than 1150 active Indian SaaS companies, 17 of which have become unicorns. According to information published by NASSCOM, the country export IT products worth \$ 178 billion in financial year 2021–2022.

In order to maintain India's position as a global leader in IT and IT-enabled services, the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology is coordinating strategic initiatives, promoting talent development programmes, expanding infrastructure capacities, and supporting R&D.

- India ranks first in software services exports, for the financial year 2022 the estimated export revenue amounts to dollar 178 billion as per the reports.
- India holds top position in digital skills readiness and is considered fastest growing center for startups and largest market share in global service industry.
- India ranks second in terms of number of internet subscribers.
- When it comes to building up Global Capabilities Centers, India is one of the most popular locations. More than 2,300 GCC units, comprising more than 1,400 plus GCCs, are located in India and employ more than 1.38 million professionals as of financial year 2021.
- By 2025, India will receive more than 45 additional data centers and \$10 billion has been invested in data centers in India since 2020.
- In terms of AI talent concentration, India secures the top spot. Moreover, India ranks fifth in both AI scientific publications and FTTH/Building Internet subscriptions.

Literature Review

1. Nirvikar Singh and Sarbjit Singh (2015), in their paper titled “**Information Technology and its Role in India’s Economic Development: A Review**” have discussed about the role of Information technology in growth of the economy and about the success of export of service sector and focused on to deliver these IT enabled services in rural area people and various e-commerce platforms for growth of each section of the society of India.

2.Arvindhan M (2019), in research paper titled “**A Research Paper on Modern Technology**” has discussed the changes in our life due to advancement in technology. In this he has found that the technology has affected our life in positive way by giving more opportunities for job, new teaching and learning pattern, work getting done easily and also discussed some negative aspect.

3 IdrishAllad and Dr. Mahendra H. Maisuria (2015), in their paper titled“**IT sector in India – Evolution, Growth and a Tool of Economic Development**” have discussed the evolution of IT sector and also highlighted the reasons for growth of IT sector in India. They have also focused on the future prospects,and also IT sector has also lead to women empowerment and reduction in gender inequalities.

Objectives

1. To study the concept and role of IT sector in Indian Economy
2. To explore the key drivers for growth of IT sector
3. To study the export value of IT sector in India
4. To find the contribution of IT sector to India’s GDP

IT Exports

With the growth of 17.02 percent, export of information technology is set to reach a target of dollar 178 billion excluding hardware. Additionally, the detail information regarding the different sector is mentioned below:

IT services: At \$95 billion, it maintains its market share dominance and is anticipated to have the highest performance in FY2021, with a y-o-y rise of 18%.

Business Processing Management: This sector is also speeding its transformation to platform solutions, with a \$39 billion market and a growth rate of 14% year over year (BPaaS to expand 4X compared to traditional BPM). Analytics, growing implementation of RPA, and automation-led services in F&A and HR are some growth drivers.

Engineering and R&D: This sector is being driven by cloud engineering, services centered around data monetization, and digital engineering. This category is being led by increased softwarization of equipment and devices ("software-led products") and cloudification. Historically, this sector has experienced the strongest growth rate; however, for FY2021, growth is anticipated to drop (17% year over year), reaching \$36 billion.

Software products: This market is expected to grow to 34% to \$7 billion as demand for collaborative apps, application platforms, security software, system & service management software, and content workflow & management applications increased.

In the fiscal year 2021, it was estimated that India would export IT services worth 149.1 US billion. With 61.4 billion dollars, the banking, financial, and insurance (BFSI) services accounted for the majority of exports. The majority of total revenue comes from IT exports, which dominate the sector. The domestic market, however, had also demonstrated optimistic developments.

In 2022, it was predicted that India's information technology industry would spend over 101 billion US dollars on various segments. The majority of the targeted investment was on equipment and telecommunications services. With more than half of the export market share in the nation, IT services were the market leader among the many divisions within the business.

Growth Drivers

The government has taken several initiatives for technological development and to enable digital services all over the country. It has focused more on some key drivers including blockchain, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, data processing and hyper-scale computing to reduce frauds and increasing transparency the government has released national strategy on blockchain. India has faced start-up revolution through artificial intelligence, machine learning, information of things and healthcare. Further, more focus is on cloud enablement and remote working. And over 1.78 lakh gram panchayats are connected by optical fiber. The figure highlights the growth drivers of information technology sector.

Contribution of IT/BPM Sector to India’s GDP

Year	GDP at current prices (in billion \$)	Revenue of IT/BPMS (in billion \$)	IT revenue to GDP ratio (in percentage)
2017-18	2651.47	167	6.298393
2018-19	2702.93	177	6.548449
2019-20	2831.55	191	6.745422
2020-21	2667.69	196	7.347181
2021-22	3176.30	227	7.14668

The above table represents the revenue of IT/BPM sector for past five years, though which IT revenue to GDP ratio was found and it was found that the ratio was in increasing trend. As per the reports published by NASSCOM, information technology has projected highest growth since 2011 and each sub-sectors have recorded growth in double digits. And the revenue is expected to increase to dollar 350 billion till 2026.

Share of IT/BPM sector in the GDP of India during FY 2009 to 2022

Source- www.statista.com

Findings and Conclusion

- The IT revenue to GDP ratio reflected an increasing trend indicating the consistent growth in the revenue of IT/BPMS
- The revenue of Information Technology sector is expected to increase up to dollar 350 billion till 2026
- With the growth of 17.02 percent, export of information technology is set to reach a target of dollar 178 billion excluding hardware.
- Information Technology has projected highest growth since 2011 and each sub-sectors have recorded growth in double digits. And the revenue is expected to increase to dollar 350 billion till 2026.

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